

Dimensions of Debris Flow of Kedarnath Disaster 2013: A Study using Digital Elevation Models

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Abstract : Located in Garhwal Himalayas, Kedarnath (3,583 m) is one of the holiest sites of Hindu pilgrimage. In the morning of 17 June 2013, Kedarnath village got devastated by a debris flow resulting from bursting of a moraine-dammed lake called Chorabari Tal, which is located 300 m above the settlement, in the northwest. In this study estimations are made to measure the breach parameters of the lake viz. lake volume, peak flow, peak flow velocity and momentum. They were estimated from SRTM, ASTER and CartoDEM elevation models. The 9–10 m-high lateral moraine ridge of the Chorabari glacier was breached along a 60-m wide stretch due to high water pressure in the lake after a high intensity rainfall received in its 2.7 km² catchment. The amount of water released was estimated at 0.43 × 10⁶ m³ (SRTM), 0.25 × 10⁶ m³ (ASTER), and 0.63 × 10⁶ m³ (CartoDEM). Using predictive equations, the peak flow was calculated for SRTM, ASTER and CartoDEM as 1352.2 m³s⁻¹, 850.2 m³s⁻¹ and 2280.3 m³s⁻¹, respectively. Within less than one minute of the bursting of the Chorabari Tal, the flow devastated the Kedarnath settlement. The 12.42° slope of the Mandakini along the 1.41 km Chorabari–Kedarnath stretch was steep enough for the initial flow of debris to attain the required momentum ranging between 21–25 × 10⁶ kgm³s⁻¹, which obliterated the northern and western parts of the settlement. Since the lake boundary and the lake watershed derived from SRTM DEM fit much better to the topographic character of the area, as noticed on the satellite images, the SRTM-derived results are considered to be the best estimates.

Key Words : GLOF, DEM, remote sensing, chorabari, kedarnath

Introduction

Debris flows are very common in a mountainous terrain. They always come without a warning and as a result the response time is minimal. Therefore, debris flows can be disastrous. Debris flows are among the most frequently occurring of natural hazards in a mountainous region (Santi et al., 2010). In general terms debris flow can be categorized as a specific type of mass movement. It may be expressed as “rapid mass movement of granular solids, water and air” (Varnes, 1978). Debris flow is an extremely hazardous phenomena that occurs when loads of unsorted sediment, saturated with water, rush down the slopes in response to gravitational attraction. The mixture of solid and liquid components influence the motion of the flow, and therefore, debris flows are distinguished from

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sediment-laden floods and other types of flows (Iverson, 1997). Debris flow generally gets guided into the stream channel and entrains everything in its path, eventually expanding the volume of the flow. Debris flow is even capable of entraining large boulders in suspension. Often, such flows could be recognised as coarse-grained sediments, pebbles and boulders along a steep, narrow and pre-existing channel (Sati, 2007). In steeper channels, the flow can attain high velocity and cause catastrophic damages. In low-gradient channels, the flow can be slow but capable to bury or destroy everything in its way (Pierson, 2005). The thickness is usually not more than a few meters.

In case of floods and flash floods, the flow behaviour is controlled by the volume of water and slope. By contrast, the flow behaviour of debris flows is significantly influenced by the entrained sediment (Pierson, 2005). Although they generally have more densities (volumetric sediment concentrations of 30-50 percent) as compared to the other types of landslides, due to widespread liquefaction of sediments caused by the presence of significant amount of water, they almost flow like water (Iverson, 1997). The extent of debris flow is directly related with the density of the transported materials and slope. Zimmermann and Haeberli (1992) emphasized that debris flow usually travels long distance and is capable of transporting large amount of debris within a short time span. Valdiya (1987) pointed that the man-made engineering structures could provide sizeable amount of debris for such transportation.

Debris flow occurs frequently in the Hindukush and Himalayas (Hewitt, 2004), often triggered by excessive rainfall events in river valleys with easily erodible materials. Glacial lake outburst flood (GLOF) is a specific type of debris flow that occurs rarely and associated with high-discharge events (Breien et al., 2008). Such an event took place recently in the Kedarnath area of the Garhwal Himalayas, where an outburst flood from Chorabari lake, formed earlier by the lateral moraine of a glacier, caused severe damage to the Kedarnath village on the morning of 17th June 2013 (Das et al., 2015). As a result of the heavy rainfall in the lake catchment area, the water level of the lake climbed above the bordering lateral moraine ridge and eventually, due to excessive pressure exerted by the volume of water, the ridge collapsed. The lake was drained out in 5–10 min (Dobhal et al., 2013) and the boulders and other rock fragments of the ridge were swept into the Mandakini River. The initial amount of debris was provided by the breached portion of the lateral moraine ridge, but as the flow reached the Mandakini valley downslope, it started to generate more debris by entraining the river bed materials and eroding the river banks. By the time it reached Kedarnath village, its shape and size got enlarged, and the momentum of the flow was so high that it destroyed almost half of the structures of the settlement and carried much of the material further downstream along the Mandakini channel. The strong force generated by the debris flow had practically wiped out the northern, western and south-western parts of the settlement. The arterial road of the settlement, leading to the Kedarnath shrine, acted as a passage for the debris flow. A huge boulder (dimension: 1.80 m x 3.05 m) miraculously got stuck behind the temple to save it from the direct impact of the flow. The south-eastern part of the settlement was least affected as it remained away from the main flow path (Das et al., 2015). The event, regarded as one of the most devastating in recorded history, caused unprecedented fatality and economic loss (Rana et al., 2013). Not only the debris flow devastated

Kedarnath within minutes, it wiped out the settlements like *Ramwada* and *Gourikund* located 7 and 14 km downstream, respectively.

Since real-time data on hydrological and geomorphological parameters of debris flow at Kedarnath were not available, many attempts were made during the last few years to presume the values from the free-access Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and by applying several predictive equations. In this study an attempt is made to measure the breach parameters, lake volume, peak flow, peak flow velocity and momentum of the flow from the DEM's of the area.

Geographical Setting

Set amidst the backdrop of snow-capped peaks of the Garhwal Himalayas, the shrine of Kedarnath is among the holiest pilgrimages for the devout Hindu. The Kedarnath temple is over a thousand years old and is built of massive stone slabs over a large rectangular platform. It has been continually renovated over the centuries. Immediately behind the shrine, the Kedarnath peak (6,940 m) and Kedarnath Dome peak (6,831 m) can be seen. The temple and the settlement associated with it are located on the terrace of the Mandakini River. The settlement is listed as a *Nagar Panchayat* in the Rudraprayag District of Uttarakhand State. Before the fateful incident, the liner extension of the settlement was 520 m and it had a southward gradient of 1:12.4 (Das et al., 2015).

The Kedarnath region is nested within the Mandakini-Saraswati watershed (Fig. 1). The Kedarnath Temple (30°44'05"N, 79°04'01"E) is located about 3,533 m above mean sea level near the snout of the Chorabari Glacier, which is also the source of the Mandakini river. The confluence of the Mandakini river and Saraswati river that originates from nearby Companion glaciers, is located about 1 km north of the village (Fig. 2). The Mandakini-Saraswati watershed extends up to Sonprayag (18 km downstream of Kedarnath), where Mandakini River converges with Basuki River (Fig. 1).

The retreat of Chorabari and Companion glaciers occurred considerably during the last few centuries and they formed lateral moraine ridges along their edges (Chaujar, 2009). Near the present snout of the Chorabari glacier, its right lateral moraine formed a barrier to a rain and snowmelt water-fed stream that occupied a small valley and thus created a 4.6-ha ephemeral lake known as the Chorabari Tal (3,845 m). It used to exist seasonally, especially during the monsoon months (June-October). The lake had no visible outlet, and it used to drain by seeping through the right lateral moraine of the Chorabari glacier. The relative setting of the Chorabari lake and Kedarnath village, although rather exceptional, played a catalyst to the debris flow-induced disaster.

Database and Methodology

Estimations regarding the relief and other area parameters of the Chorabari lake and its outlet through the breached moraine ridge were carried out with three free-access digital elevation data sets from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global DEM and CartoDEM programmes (Table 1). Georeferencing and overlay operations of the images were carried out for extraction of lake catchment area, height of moraine dam above the lake bed and bankful capacity of the lake (Table 2).

Figure 1: Location of Chorabari Lake and Kedarnath settlement within Chorabari-Mandakini watershed.

Figure 2: Geographic and Physiographic setting of Kedarnath and its surrounding area (d) located in Rudraprayag District (c) of Uttarakhand (b), India (a). Elevation map prepared from SRTM VIDEEM

Table 1: Elevation and Image Data used in the Study

Data particulars	Imaging date	Average Resolution	Scene or tile ID	Data source
SRTM DEM	11 Feb 2000	85.1 m	SRTM3N30E079V1	earthexplorer.usgs.gov
ASTER GDEM v2	2000~2009	28.7 m	ASTGDEMv2_0N30E079	earthexplorer.usgs.gov
Cartosat-1 DEM (CartoDEM) v1	2006~2008	28.6 m	H44H	bhuvan-noeda.nrsc.gov.in/download/download/download.php/
Bing image ¹	Nov 2009	~1 m	—	www.bing.com/maps imaging date from: http://mvexel.dev.openstreetmap.org/bing/
Cartosat-2 Pan + LISS-4mx	25 Jun 2013	~1 m	—	bhuvan3.nrsc.gov.in

Note: 1. Satellite information and exact date of pass of this image not available.

Source : Compiled by the authors

Prediction of quantitative dimensions of debris flow, following the dam breach, were attempted by many scholars (Table 3). The major concerns comprise the flow volume, peak discharge, breach width and height, failure time, front velocity of the flow, travel distance, and flow routing, etc. (Rickenmann, 1999; Wahl, 2004; Westoby et al., 2014). Prediction of peak discharge (Q_p) is made by a number of projecting equations given by various scholars (Table 3). The parameters taken are storage (S), height of water (H), breach width (B) and gravity (g). These equations are clustered into four categories where peak discharge is considered as function (f) of various parameters:

$$Q_p = f(H)$$

$$Q_p = f(S)$$

$$Q_p = f(H, S)$$

$$Q_p = f(H, B, g)$$

The flow is presumed to be a Newtonian turbulent flow. From empirical observation values, Manning coefficient (n) for debris flow is considered as 0.1 (Pierson, 1986; PWRI, 1988; Rickenmann and Zimmermann, 1993; Rickenmann, 1999). With this consideration the debris flow velocity (V) is predicted by the equation provided by PWRI (1988) As:

$$V = (1/n) H^{0.67} S^{0.5}$$

Where, H = Depth of the flow; S = Slope.

Momentum of the flow when it struck Keadarnath was estimated assuming the density of the flow as 1922 kg/m^3 (density of sand soaked with water, www.engineeringtoolbox.com) as the debris comprised very fine clay to large rock chunks (Table 4).

Table 2: Parameters of Chorabari Lake Estimated from Elevation Data.

DEM	Catchment area (sq km)	Bounding contour (m)	Area (sq m)	Max Elevation (m)	Min Elevation (m)	Max water level (m)	Breach width (m) - Bhuvan	Breach wall-top elevation (m)	Breach base elevation (m)	Breach Height (m)	Breach cross sectional area (sq m)	Volume at bankfull stage (m ³)	Estimated rain (mm) in last 24 hrs over catchment to reach bankfull	Derived hourly avg rainfall (mm)
SRTM	2.91	3857	45948	3857	3845	12	60	3857	3847	10	600	434088	149	6.22
ASTER	2.67	3861	41019	3861	3846	15	60	3861	3851	10	600	247905	93	3.87
CARTOSAT	2.71	3838	66753	3838	3827	11	60	3838	3829	9	540	618838	228	9.51

Source : Estimated from elevation data

To compare the pre- and post-event scenarios of the area, two cloud-free high-resolution satellite images of 2009 (Bing Maps) and 2013 (Cartosat-2 Pan + LISS-4mx, Bhuvan) were used.

Results and Discussion

As per Dobhal et al. (2013), on 17th June 2013 the breaching of the Chorabari lake was initiated by overtopping of the accumulated water over the lateral moraine ridge bounding the lake on the south (Fig. 3). According to our DEM-based measurements, on the southeast of the lake the lowest absolute height of the ridge is 3,857 m (SRTM), 3,861 m (ASTER), and 3,838 m (CartoDEM). Indicated by the merged Cartosat-2 Pan + LISS-4mx image of 25 June 2013 this point closely coincides with the location of breaching in all three DEMs (Fig. 4). The lowest relative height of the ridge from the lake bed amounted to 12 m (SRTM) 15 m (ASTER) and 11 m (CartoDEM). Contours are generated with the help of these values to find out the bankful capacity of the lake prior to its breaching (Fig. 4). In case of SRTM, ASTER and CartoDEM the values amounted to 0.43×10^6 m³, 0.25×10^6 m³, and 0.63×10^6 m³, respectively. Breach height was measured for each DEM from the elevation difference between the top and the base of the moraine ridge at breach site which was 10 m for SRTM and ASTER, and 9 m for CartoDEM. Breach width (60 m) was estimated from post-event Cartosat-2 Pan + LISS-4mx, Bhuvan image (Table 2).

Without considering loss from seepage or evaporation, it is predicted by the DEM-derived information, that to fill the Chorabari lake up to its capacity 149 mm (SRTM), 93 mm (ASTER) and 228 mm (CartoDEM) of rainfall would require in its catchment area (Table 2). As reported by Dobhal et al. (2013), gain from antecedent water already present in the lake and snow from the last season is not taken into consideration due to absence of any data. The

Figure 3: Pre (a) and post (b) event conditions of Kedarnath area showing the breached lateral moraine ridge of Chorabari lake and debris flow paths.

Figure 4: Pre (a)- and post (b) -GLOF images of the Chorabari lake region. 1. Sita hill; 2. Flattish lake bed in the dry post-monsoon season; 3. Right lateral moraine of the Chorabari glacier; 4. Breached portion of the moraine ridge with incised channels that scoured the lacustrine deposits during draining of the lake. Extents of the lake at full capacity are shown in a as extracted from the three DEMs. The perimeter derived from the SRTM DEM matches with the topography most suitably.

Table 3: GLOF Peak Discharge and Lake Volume Derived from Elevation Data and Predictive Equations

Equation	SRTM		ASTER		CartoDEM				
	Peak Flow (cumec)	Computed storage volume from peak discharge ¹ (m ³)	Percentage difference of computed storage volume from DEM-derived storage volume ²	Peak Flow (cumec)	Computed storage volume from peak discharge ¹ (m ³)	Percentage difference of computed storage volume from DEM-derived storage volume ²	Peak Flow (cumec)	Computed storage volume from peak discharge ¹ (m ³)	Percentage difference of computed storage volume from DEM-derived storage volume ²
Category-1: peak discharge as a function of height of water									
Kirkpatrick (1977) Qp=1.268(H+0.3)2.5	431.7	129303.2	-70.2	431.7	129734.9	-47.7	334.4	100166.7	-83.8
US Soil Conservation (1981) Qp=16.6(H)1.85	1175.2	351969.4	-18.9	1175.2	353144.6	42.5	967.1	289636.7	-53.2
US Bureau of reclamations (1982) Qp=19.1(H)1.85	1352.2	404976.8	-6.7	1352.2	406329.1	63.9	1112.7	333256.7	-46.1
Singh and Snorasson (1982) Qp=13.4(H)1.89	1040.2	311531.3	-28.2	1040.2	312571.3	26.1	852.4	255281.9	-58.7
Walder and O'Connor (1997) Qp= 60.3(H)0.84	417.2	124943.6	-71.2	417.2	125360.8	-49.4	381.8	114361.0	-81.5
Pierce et.al (2010) Qp= 0.784(H)2.688	382.2	114475.6	-73.6	382.2	114857.9	-53.7	288.0	86241.6	-86.1
Category-2: peak discharge as a function of storage									
Singh and Snorasson (1984) Qp= 1.776(V)0.47	792.7	237411.2	-45.3	609.2	183063.5	-26.2	936.4	280466.6	-54.7
Evans (1986)Qp= 0.72(V)0.53	700.2	209722.7	-51.7	520.4	156368.1	-36.9	845.0	253084.3	-59.1
Walder and O'Connor (1997) Qp= 0.045(V)0.66	236.6	70861.5	-83.7	163.5	49123.1	-80.2	299.0	89546.9	-85.5
Costa (1985) Qp= 1.22(V)0.57	1994.2	597277.1	37.6	1449.1	435458.9	75.7	2440.9	731064.5	18.1

Table 3: contd....

Category-3: peak discharge as a function of height of water and storage										
Hagen (1982) $Q_p=0.54(VH)^{0.5}$	1125.1	336960.8	-22.4	850.2	255494.2	3.1	1274.4	381680.9	-38.3	
McDonald and L.-Monopolis (1984) $Q_p=1.154(VH)^{0.412}$	626.5	187622.4	-56.8	497.3	149450.1	-39.7	694.2	207912.4	-66.4	
McDonald and L.-Monopolis (1984) $Q_p=3.85(VH)^{0.411}$	2058.3	616455.8	42.0	1635.0	491311.2	98.2	2280.3	682950.9	10.4	
Costa (1985) $Q_p=0.981(VH)^{0.42}$	601.8	180238.9	-58.5	475.6	142926.7	-42.3	668.2	200129.1	-67.7	
Costa (1985) $Q_p=2.634(VH)^{0.44}$	2193.6	656971.8	51.3	1714.4	515164.5	107.8	2447.8	733117.0	18.5	
Froehlich (1995) $Q_p=0.607(V^{0.295}H^{1.24})$	485.6	145435.7	-66.5	411.6	123693.7	-50.1	473.1	141697.3	-77.1	
Walder and O'Connor (1997) $Q_p=0.19(VH)^{0.47}$	250.3	74956.9	-82.7	192.3	57797.9	-76.7	281.4	84272.5	-86.4	
Pierce et al (2010) $Q_p=0.0176(VH)^{0.606}$	185.3	55498.5	-87.2	132.0	39654.7	-84.0	215.5	64547.0	-89.6	
Pierce et al (2010) $Q_p=0.038(V^{0.475}H^{1.09})$	222.7	66685.2	-84.6	170.6	51276.0	-79.3	234.9	70356.5	-88.6	
Category-4: peak discharge as a function of breach cross section area and gravity										
Hungr et al (1984) $Q_p=0.3 B g^{0.5}Hr^{1.5}$	1783	533954	23	1783	535737	116	1522	455898	-26	

Source

 Q_p : Peak discharge; S: Storage; H: Height of water; B: Breach width; g: gravitational acceleration

Notes: 1. Based on the assumption that the lake completely drained in 10 min and that the discharge diminished linearly from the peak (see text for further explanation).

2. Values closest to zero indicate closest fit of the storage volume computed from peak discharge with storage volume estimated from respective DEMs (Table 2).

estimates range from 29 percent to 70 percent of 325 mm—the recorded rainfall of 24-h period up to 17:00 of 16 June 2013 (Dobhal et al., 2013)—indicating enormous loss from seepage through the porous morainic material. So, the actual rainfall in the area was more than enough for filling the lake up to its storage capacity.

Following Haeberli (1983), it is assumed that the initial discharge subsequent to the breach is the highest (peak discharge, Q_p) as he noted that in case of glacial dam burst, peak discharge coincides with the frontal wave following the breach. Reliability of the results derived from the predictive equations are evaluated by comparing them with the observation that after reaching the peak discharge at breach site, the lake emptied in the next 10 minutes, which is the outer limit of draining time mentioned by Dobhal et al. (2013). By integrating a linearly decreasing discharge rate during a 10-minute period, the total volume of water discharged from the lake was measured for each equation. Subsequently a comparison was made with the bank-full volume of discharge derived for the 10-minute period with the volume of lake water estimated from the DEM (Table 2). The most appropriate estimation are found for SRTM was derived using parameter values and equations given by the United States Bureau of Reclamations (1982) of the first category, for ASTER it was the equation given by Hagen (1982) of the third category, and for CartoDEM it was the equation given by McDonald and L-Monopolis (1984) of the third category. Percentage difference of computed storage volume from DEM-derived storage volume came 6.7 percent for SRTM, 3.1 percent for ASTER and 10.4 percent for Carto DEM (Table 3).

From the breached portion of the moraine ridge, Kedarnath is situated 300 m lower than the lowest level of the Chorabari lake. The debris flow generated by the GLOF typically tracked 1.41 km of existing channels to reach the northern end of the village following a mean slope of 12.42 degree. Peak flow velocity and momentum of initial thrust at the time the flow struck Kedarnath is estimated for the three applicable peak flow predictions derived from three DEMs (Table 4). In all three cases it is found that within less than one minute of the bursting of the Chorabari Tal, the flow devastated the Kedarnath settlement. The momentum of the initial thrust predicted to be ranging between $21-25 \times 10^6 \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Table 4: Downstream Parameters of the Debris Flow Estimated from Elevation Data

	Peak flow	Breach Height (m)	Slope(Degree) from Chorabari lake to Kedarnath settlement	Velocity at breach site (m s^{-1})	Velocity at northern edge of Kedarnath (m s^{-1})	Momentum of the flow at northern edge of Kedarnath ($\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
SRTM	1352.2	10	12.42	2.25	21.78	25116696.0
ASTER	850.2	10	12.42	1.41	21.78	25116696.0
CARTOSAT	2280.3	9	12.42	4.23	20.29	21058585.2

Source : Compiled by the authors

From the comparison of pre-and post-event images of Kedarnath village, downstream consequences of the debris flow are marked by Das et al. (2015). The north-western section of the hamlet falls on the direct path of the debris flow and almost all structures of this area were totally demolished or fully buried. Most of the partially damaged structures occupied the area adjacent to and downslope of the annihilated part of the settlement. The southern and southeastern sections of the village were least affected. Out of 37,299 m² of pre-event roof-area of Kedarnath (259 structures), 44.2 percent were completely destroyed and 26.7 percent were partly damaged, representing 138 and 56 structures, respectively (Das et al., 2015). At northern part of the settlement, the Kedarnath temple, built by massive granite, was able to withstand the debris flow. The flow faced resistance by the concrete structures before reaching the temple.

Limitations of the estimates

No primary field survey or Ground Truth Verification (GTV) could be carried out by the authors during or after the disaster, which seriously compromised the results. Other limitations are:

1. Cross section dimension of breach site was taken as the flow cross sectional area from breach site to Kedarnath.
2. Constrictions and directional changes of flow could not be considered.
3. Some very important parameters like density, viscosity, grain concentration of the debris flow were not known, hence were estimated for the study.
4. Channel configuration at the northern part of Kedarnath could not be considered.
5. Haeberli (1983) noted that the outflowing water may incorporate sediments which can result in a bulking of the total volume up to about a factor of two for glacier outburst floods. This factor was not taken into consideration.

Concluding Note

With lack of field data, it is difficult to determine the accuracy of any of the DEMs from the derived information. Regarding vertical accuracy, concerns remain with most types of freely available DEMs on regional scale.

In the present study area the lake boundary as well as the lake watershed derived from SRTM DEM fit better to the topography derived from satellite images compared to the other two datasets (Figure 4). The SRTM-derived results (Table 3), therefore, can be considered as the best estimates among the three available DEMs, despite its coarser resolution.

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